

Microcanonical Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Part II

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In a previous note (1), we tried to calculate the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution from microcanonical considerations. We found that if Stirling's approximation is used and $e \ll E_{\text{total}}$, one obtains $P(e) = C \exp(-e/a)$. This still requires that one find C and "a" through constraints i.e. Integral phase space $C \exp(-e/a) = 1$ and Integral phase space $C e \exp(-e/a) = E/N$. What seems to be interesting in the microcanonical approach, however, is that $\exp(-e/a)$ is not the single particle probability for e close to E (say $E = e/5$ etc). In fact, it seems that for N not too large (200 or so), there are correlations between single particle energies for e close to E . If one particle has an energy almost equal to E , this restricts the energies of other particles. Thus, the idea of maximum uncertainty does not seem to apply in such cases. This has implications on scattering probabilities given by $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ for small N equilibrium. Furthermore, it affects on factorial schemes which are maximized subject to energy and particle number constraints for small N . In this note, we try to examine some of these factors.

Maximum Uncertainty

The idea of maximum uncertainty seems to be used in statistical mechanics and information theory. The distribution $\exp(-e/T)$ is an example of such a result i.e. it follows from maximizing $f(e)$:

$$\text{Product over } i \ f(e_i)^{N f(e_i)} \text{ subject to } \text{Sum over } i \ e_i f(e_i) = E \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i \ f(e_i) = N. \quad ((1))$$

If one considers a microcanonical distribution (as in (1)), one finds, however, that particle energies are correlated for small N (100, 200 or smaller) and that different ideas may be important. In many cases, the MB distribution is applied to very large numbers of particles and so is a good approximation for all e as a single particle never approaches an energy of E . Statistical mechanical ideas, however, have also been applied to systems with smaller numbers, such as nucleons in a nucleus etc and there have also been articles in the literature (2) dealing with maximization of arrangements in the case of small particle numbers.

Traditional Small Particle Number Approaches

Traditional small particle number approaches seem to lead to $\exp(-e/T)$ type solutions. For example, if one assumes the probability for two particles to collide is $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ and imposes reaction balance, then:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ with } e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2))$$

This immediately leads to an $\exp(-e/T)$ type solution, but $f(e_i)$ represents a “fictitious” equilibrium state that represents a time average applied to one point in time.

Factorial schemes used in (2) also lead to a similar $\exp(-e/T)$ type solution. For example, consider maximizing:

$$\ln\{M! / [m_1! M_2! M_3]\} \text{ subject to } \sum \text{ over } i \ m_i = N \text{ and } \sum \text{ over } i \ e_i m_i = E \quad ((3))$$

For small particle numbers, one cannot use Stirling’s approximation, neither can one take a regular derivative. One may, however, use:

$\ln((m_1+1)!) - \ln(m_1!) = \ln(m_1+1)$ as a type of derivative. In such a case, maximization yields:

$$\ln(m_1+1) + b_1 m_1 + b_2 e_1 m_1 = 0 \quad ((4)) \text{ which yields an } \exp(-e/T) \text{ type solution.}$$

Microcanonical Solution for Small Particle Numbers

In (1), it was argued one could write the microcanonical number of arrangements of N particles with a total energy E as:

$$(E/a + V-1)! / [(V-1)! (E/a)!] \quad ((4))$$

Here V is the number of interior partitions and “ a ” the minimum amount of energy that may be transferred in a collision. If one uses N instead of V and applies Stirling’s approximation for E/a replaced with $E/a - e/a$ and V replaced with $N-1$, one obtains $P(e) = C \exp[-e/ (E/N)]$. In such a case, E/N is not T and one does not use energy density. Instead V is used. One may place a certain number of E/a energy units into various partitions. For example, there could be a partition with 3 E/a units and another also with 3 E/a units. Ultimately, each energy interval must be associated with a phase space of $dp_x dp_y dp_z V / \text{constant}$, where the constant is related to Planck’s constant. In such a case, using Stirling’s approximation and replacing E/a with $E/a - e/a$ and V with $V-1$ yields:

$$P(e) = C \exp[-e/ (E/(V-1))] \quad ((5))$$

One may then use: $\int \text{Integral phase space } C \exp[-e/ (E/V)] = 1$ and $\int \text{Integral phase space } C e \exp[-e/ (E/V)] = E/N$.

The two normalizations used, however, are approximations.

It should be noted that three approximations are used to obtain the MB type probability density above. First, Stirling’s approximation is used to replace the factorial, secondly one use a Taylor’s series to expand a term like $\ln(E/a - e/a)$ to first order and thirdly, one approximates $\exp[-e / (E/V)]$ by $[1 - e/ (E/V)]$. It seems these approximations do not hold for all cases of e .

First of all, if one has few particles, then it is possible to have an arrangement with one particle possessing almost all of the energy. In such a case, $E/a - e/a$ becomes a small number and one cannot use Stirling's approximation. Thus, it seems $\exp[-e / (E/V)]$ does not apply to the tail of the $P(e)$ distribution. For e almost E there would be only one arrangement after removing e , namely all particles having an energy of almost 0.

Secondly, even if one can use Stirling's approximation, one still has to consider:

$$\ln(E/a - e/a + V-1) \text{ and } \ln(E/a - e/a) \quad ((6))$$

$E/a - e/a$ may be a large number because "a" is very small, but e is not necessarily small compared with E e.g. $e=E/6$. (For large N systems, one does not really have this issue.) In such a case, one may not be able to make a first order Taylor expansion of $\ln(E/a - e/a + V-1)$ and $\ln(E/a - e/a)$. It might be necessary to retain higher terms which should lead to a deviation from the MB exponential form.

Alternatively, one may write the full expression:

$$P(e) = C [E - e + d]^{(E - e + d)/a} / \{ \ln((V-1)!) (E - e)^{(E - e)/a} \} \quad \text{where } d = (V-1)a \text{ which is very small}$$

$$\text{Or } P(e) = C_1 (E - e)^{V-1} \exp\{ (V-1)[1 + d/(E - e)] \} = C_1 (E - e)^{V-1} \exp[d/(E - e)] \quad ((7))$$

(For e small with respect to E , $(E - e)^{V-1}$ may be written as $\exp((V-1)\ln(E - e))$ and $\ln(E - e)$ expanded into $\ln(E) - e/E$. Also $1/(E - e)$ becomes $1/E (1 + e/E)$ so one obtains an $\exp(-e/b)$ form.)

Thus, ((7)) seems to imply a power law drop-off for large single particle e if d is small, where e cannot be larger than E . In order to determine parameter values, one needs to choose a cutoff e and match ((5)) and ((7)). In addition, the conditions of ((5)) (energy and normalization) have to apply.

Experimentally, ((7)) may have consequences for the evaporation of nucleons from hot large nuclei produced in heavy ion reactions.

Affect on Collision Balance

If one uses ((5)) one sees that $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4)$ for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. The conservation law must hold for all reactions. What happens if a very small e_1 collides with a large e_2 to create an intermediate e_3 and e_4 . It seems that ((5)) applies to e_1 and ((7)) to e_2 , e_3 and e_4 . If one applies ((5)) to large energy collisions, one sees that it leads to $\exp(-e/T)$ for e being very large. The equilibrium state represented by $f(e) = P(e)$, however, is a fictitious one for small N because it is a time average which is presented as existing at one point in time. It is not possible to have all energies represented at a single time t , even though each has a probability $P(e)$. Thus, the

idea of reaction balance for high e may be creating an artificial tail in the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. From ((7)), one sees that $P(e)$ for high e is not $\exp(-e/T)$, thus there is no reaction balance. If one does not allow for all total energies as in the canonical approach, one needs to have an energy cutoff in two body scattering reactions. Thus, for low energies $e=e_1+e_2$, all possible combinations of e_i and e_j are possible and have equal probability if $e_i+e_j=e$. For large energies, this is not possible because even though $P(E/2)$ and $P(2E/3)$ exist, one cannot have a collision of the two in the fictitious equilibrium state that would produce a particle with energy greater than E , the total energy of the system. Thus, there is not complete uncertainty in reaction products for higher energy. As a result, common statistical ideas seem to break down somewhat for high energies in low N systems. (For high N systems, E/N (which is proportional to T) is small, so one may have single particle energies with the MB distribution $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e=nT$ with n being a say 5, 10 etc. Experiments have also been done showing that the MB distribution is highly accurate for large numbers of particles.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a microcanonical approach suggests that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e/T)$ only holds for $e \ll E$. For large N systems, this seems to always be the case because T is of the order of E/N . For smaller N systems, e.g. nucleons in a nucleus, however, it may be necessary to use a different result for e of the order of E which seems to follow from the microcanonical approach which suggests a power law drops i.e. $(E-e)^{V-1}$. This might be observable by examining the evaporation of nucleons from hot nuclei after high energy collisions.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Microcanonical Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution? (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Miranda, E.N. Statistical Mechanics of Few Particle Systems: Exact Results for Two Useful Models European Journal of Physics Researchgate (2017)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318758580_Statistical_mechanics_of_few-particle_systems_Exact_results_for_two_useful_models